

Harmful Algae News

AN IOC NEWSLETTER ON TOXIC ALGAE AND ALGAL BLOOMS

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Highlights of the XVII International Conference on Harmful Algae

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Gambierdiscus cells on a cnidarian colony (see p 14)

Florianópolis, “Floripa” to the locals, is the capital city of the state of Santa Catarina, in southern Brazil. Many small commercial fishermen populate the island, and the fishing boats, the folklore, the cuisine and the colonial architecture contribute to make it a very attractive tourist resource for many Brazilians and Argentineans escaping from overpopulated cities. But most important for us, the Florianópolis area is the major producer of cultured oysters and mussels in the country and suffers from periodic harmful algal bloom events caused by *Alexandrium*, *Dinophysis* and *Gymnodinium* species. All this contributed to make the Brazilian colleagues choose Floripa as the venue for the XVII International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA 17), 9-14 October 2016, the first one to be held in Latin America.

ICHA 17 was hosted by *The Federal Institute of Santa Catarina* (IF-SC). The local organizing committee was chaired by Dr Luis Antonio Proença. The theme of the conference was: “Harmful Algae, from cells to fisheries: species, toxins, ecology, management and new technologies”

The Conference was attended by 350 participants from 35 countries. There were 2 keynote speakers, 8 plenary speakers, 145 oral presentations, 20 fast-talks, 250 posters and a heavily attended round table to discuss about the recent events in Chile.

The outstanding topics of the Conference were:

- **Climate anomalies**, global change, record blooms, heavily influenced by the dramatic salmon-kills and PSP events suffered by Chilean producers in 2016.
- **Advanced ‘omics** and in situ sensors, enabling tests of and answers to scientific questions that had been limited by technology
- **Cyanobacteria**: over 60 contributions. Not surprising considering that cyanobacterial toxins have been traditionally the main threat to public health of Brazilian freshwater bodies.

The “words cloud” generated from titles and keywords from oral and poster contributions illustrates well the dominant issues. As usual, *Alexandrium*, in particular the highly toxic *Alexandrium*

At the Public Market during the 17th National Oyster Festival in Florianópolis: Left, hanging baskets of oysters and scallops and right, mussel seed collectors (Photo Yolanda Pazos).

catenella (= *Alexandrium fundyense* or *Alexandrium* Group 1) was the predominant genus, followed by an increasing number of contributions on benthic HABs (*Gambierdiscus* + *Ostreopsis*) and *Dinophysis*, now matching those of *Pseudo-nitzschia*. Morphological, taxinological and genetic descriptions of SPECIES were top of the list. Emerging (cyclic imines) toxins, cyanobacterial microcystins and the arduous identification of fish-killing substances attracted much attention. The location of the venue favoured a good list of contributions from Chile, Argentina, Uruguay and Mexico in addition to those from the host country.

Detailed scientific highlights of different conference topics were prepared by senior participants to summarize the main research and management advances for the HAB scientific community, especially for those who were not able to make it to Floripa.

Beatriz Reguera (IEO, Vigo, Spain) & Luis Proença (IF-SC, Santa Catarina, Brazil)

HABs in a Changing Climate

Much of the session focused on the extraordinary natural bloom events in 2015-2016, including in Chile, the Western USA, and the eastern coastline of Tasmania.

There is a long history of *Alexandrium* blooms along the Chilean coast, and the more recent blooms have progressed northwards up the coast over

the past several decades (**Alejandro Clement, Leonardo Guzmán**). The extraordinary bloom of *Pseudochattonella verruculosa* and *Alexandrium catenella* in 2016 began in the outer coastal waters and was transported into the inland sea region, where it devastated fish farms leading to economic and social upheavals. There is a long history of *Alexandrium catenella* along the Chilean open coast, going back over 40 years of records, so the bloom stemmed from shifting environmental conditions rather than recent species introduction. The event coincided with an anomalous movement of the southeast Pacific high pressure region offshore linked to the Pacific Decadal Oscillation, suggesting there may be a climatic link that enhanced this bloom event.

Blooms of a more toxic *Alexandrium* species, *Alexandrium* Group 1 (*A. catenella* = *A. fundyense*), along the eastern coast of Tasmania appeared in 2012, for the first time in over 30 years of observations, and expanded greatly in 2015 and 2016. This coastal region is a climate change “hotspot”, resulting from the southward movement of the East Australian Current, bringing more warm water further south. The working hypothesis is that the recent appearance of the more toxic *Alexandrium* strain is the consequence of a complex interaction of increased temperature, flood events and changes in the southward extension of the East Australian Current enhancing growth of the ende-

mic, but rare, more toxic strain. (**Gu-
staaf Hallegraeff**)

The massive *Pseudo-nitzschia* bloom event along the western USA also appears to be associated with an anomalous warm “blob” of surface waters that pushed onto, and retracted from, the entire coastal region. Data suggest that these anomalous warm conditions inshore led to the selection of *Pseudo-nitzschia* over other diatoms in the near shore waters, due to their competitive ability at low nutrient concentrations. As the warm waters retracted with the onset of upwelling, this seed population of *Pseudo-nitzschia* was stimulated and sustained to create the bloom conditions along the entire coastline. (**Vera Trainer**)

There is laboratory evidence of a potential link between increasing ocean acidification, nutrient limitation and toxicity of phytoplankton. Although dinoflagellates and cyanobacteria are anticipated to benefit from increasing pCO₂, by reducing the need for energy-consuming carbon concentrating mechanisms, the expected benefits are small for *Alexandrium fundyense* and *Scrippsiella trochoidea*. However, decreased pH enhanced N assimilation under N limiting conditions, leading to increased toxin production. The findings suggest that ocean acidification may lessen the negative effects of N limitation and influence the composition and toxicity of phytoplankton assemblages. (**Dedmer Van de Waal**)

Warming of the surface ocean has

coincided with the increasing presence of HABs globally over the last 3 decades, and modelling of the optimal growth conditions of *Cochlodinium*, *Dinophysis*, and *Alexandrium* shows expansion of the optimal growth conditions and bloom windows in the Atlantic and Pacific regions by more than a month between 1982 and 2015. While ocean warming is expanding the niche for HABs, coinciding with increasing HAB frequency, the mechanistic for this linkage is not understood. (**Chris Gobler**)

Studying anomalous HAB blooms, or HAB “weather”, can provide insights to how climate pressures might affect HABs in the future, but forecasting climate driven changes in HABs will require new research approaches. Improved response planning for extraordinary HAB events, better focus Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) projections for regional changing conditions, and unification of experimental methods will be necessary if we are to move forward quickly enough to forecast, rather than hindcast, the effect of climate on HABs. (**Mark Wells**)

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Taxonomy at the XVII ICHA

The word ‘species’ appears 550 times in the abstract book of the conference, pointing at the importance of giving names and assessing relationships between the entities around which harmful algae science accumulates. Yet still

many taxa exist without our recognition. Indeed a steady number of new species are introduced at each ICHA as well as in the intersessional periods, which reminds us that our knowledge on the diversity of harmful algae is still work in progress. Luckily and despite the long blamed taxonomy crisis there are still scientists that are able to recognise the novelties and produce nice accounts of shapes and patterns that allow other scientist to recognize them too. This time also we were presented with new players in the game of HABs.

A new, non-toxic species of *Alexandrium*, *A. fragae* was described from Brazilian waters, along with the first finding of *A. tamutum* in the same area (**Suema Branco**). The new species morphologically resembles some Mediterranean forms of *A. minutum* that have a smooth epitheca and heavy reticulated hypotheca, which were shown at the ICHA conference in Lund [1]. Two new *Gambierdiscus*, *G. balechii* and *G. lapillus* were identified, the former in Celebes Sea (**Santiago Fraga**) and the latter in the Great Barrier Reef (Australia) (**Anna Liza Kretzschmar**), further raising the number of species in a genus considered as monospecific until a few years ago. Another new microbenthic species, *Ostreopsis rhodesae* from East Australian Coast was introduced (**Arjun Verma**). Although no palytoxin-like molecules were produced in this species, transcripts related to polyketide synthases (PKSs) and non-ribosomal peptide synthases (NRPSs) multi-enzyme complexes were found, which are active in the synthesis of palytoxin-like substances. The recently described *Ostreopsis fattorussoi* [2] instead does produce ovatoxins.

Diversity knowledge is growing at a very high pace also in the plankton genus *Azadinium* (**Urban Tillmann**), where 11 species have been recognised in 7 years since its establishment, some of which (e.g. *A. poporum*) are quite widespread worldwide. We can blame the small size of these species (generally < 15 µm) for the late recognition of so much diversity, which may also explain why the discovery of the real culprit of azaspiracid production took some time. Interestingly, some of the 10 species in the related genus *Amphidoma* also produce AZAs. A new entry is registered also in naked dinoflagellates with a

Birds of a feather flock together. Prof Moestrup and other well known taxonomists solving nomenclature problems (Photo Mathias Schramm)

still unnamed woloszynskioid species showing characters intermediate between the families Borghiellaceae and Suessiaceae (**Kazuya Takahashi**).

The fast evolution of molecular approaches at times may show contrasting scenarios over time: despite distinct morphologies: three *Chattonella* species, *C. antiqua*, *C. marina*, *C. ovata* had been merged in a single species based on the identity of most molecular markers [3]. Now, using a more sensitive technique relying on microsatellites – ISSR genotyping by sequencing (MIG-seq) analysis—it is shown that the three can be at least identified molecularly, although this does not prove they are separate species (**Satoshi Nagai**). With all these novelty and due to some taxonomic changes, it is not surprising that to keep the IOC taxonomic list of Harmful Species updated is a hard job (**Øjvind Moestrup**).

Montresor M et al 1990. In: Granéli E et al (eds) *Toxic marine phytoplankton* (Elsevier, Amsterdam) pp 82-87

Accoroni S et al 2016. *J Phycol*: doi:10.1111/jpy.12464

Demura M et al 2009. *Phycologia* 48: 518-535

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Benthic HABs

Benthic harmful algal blooms (BHABs) have an increasing interest based primarily in ciguatera but also due to problems caused by *Ostreopsis* in some coastal waters. The knowledge of the ecology of benthic microalgae is far from the well developed studies on plankton ecology, but some important progresses in the ecology of *Gambierdiscus* (**Chui Pin Leaw, Masao Adachi, Michaela Larsson, Ingrid Sassenhagen**) was presented as well as in modelling *Gambierdiscus* bloom dynamics (**Michael Parsons, Steven Kibler**). In parallel to the description of new *Gambierdiscus* species, the known distribution of the genus has increased considerably including some new reports: Cuba (**Lisbet Díaz Asencio, Angel Moreira**), El Salvador (**Rebeca Quintanilla**), Colombian Caribbean (**Anderson Ruiz Gómez**), Brazil (**Silvia Nascimento**), Philippines (**Rhodora Azanza**) Indonesia (**Santiago Fraga**) and Canary Islands (**Francisco Rodríguez**), and

SEM micrograph of *Gambierdiscus balechii* (Photo Santiago Fraga).

their expansion to new areas (**Michaela Larsson**). For the first time, the transfer of *Gambierdiscus* toxins to herbivorous fish in laboratory conditions was studied and clearly demonstrated (**Rachel Clausung**).

Far from the planktonic HABs is the monitoring of BHABs. *Gambierdiscus* monitoring was only reported from the Philippines (**Ma Llorina Rañada**) but due to the efforts of IAEA on training scientist of many countries (**Yasmine Bottein**) the implementation of BHABs monitoring programs in the near future can be expected.

Although ciguatera is the most important harmful effect of benthic algal blooms, other genera like *Ostreopsis* may cause harm when some blooms of species of this genus were related to human respiratory problems. Reports of the presence of *Ostreopsis* were abundant from many countries and the presence of toxic and non toxic species was reported (**Olga Carnicer, Cristina Mendes, Silvia Nascimento, Mariana Santos**). Progress in the study of the *Ostreopsis* bloom conditions and/or associated macroalgae were reported (**Rodolphe Lemée, Daniela Catania, Stefano Accoroni, Chui Pin Leaw, Elisa Berdalet**).

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Cyanobacteria

Over 60 studies were presented and distributed in 5 main areas: i) Toxins analysis; Surveillance and management; iii) Ecology and bloom dynamics; iv) Toxicology; v) Cell physiology and vi) Others.

New reports about human oral exposure in different continents (South America and Africa) were presented including relevant case studies about recreational exposure to microcystins in Mozambique (**Olivia Pedro**) and Uruguay (**Daniela Sedan**). The later represented a serious health risk that included a case of a child suffering fulminant hepatitis requiring a liver transplant.

Advances on cyanobacterial cell physiology and intraspecific diversity analysis were given by **Iame Guedes** and **Elena Galvanese**. Other highlights included: Nodularin records in South America (**Luiza Costa, Savênia Silveira**); increasing surveillance and management data from different regions and continued exploration of clay and flocculants for removing cells and/or cyanotoxins (**Valeria Magalhães, Cinthia Bogarín**)

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Percentage of contributions on different issues related to Cyanobacteria.

HABs Biology and Ecology

The recent advent of 'omics' technologies made possible the exploration of additional features to understand functional aspects of the biology and physiology of harmful species (reviewed in next section on molecular technologies), including the intricate sexual reproduction of *Pseudo-nitzschia* species (**Marina Montresor** keynote speech).

There was a good session about the diversity and role of parasites affecting various dinoflagellate (host) species with different susceptibility (**Esther Garcés**, **Albert Reñé**). In the field, recurrent blooms of *Alexandrium pacificum* in the Marlborough Sounds of South Island New Zealand were described. While hydrological modelling of the bloom environments were successful, biological modelling showed far less success. Bloom termination tended to be by encystment, but complications associated with parasitism may have accounted for the difficulty in the biological modelling (**Lincoln MacKenzie**).

The role of β -N-methylamino-L-alanine (BMAA), the producer organism and their actual effects, continue to be a mystery (**Sandra Lage**).

Allelopathic interactions received considerable attention. Algicidal bacteria act on HABs, particularly those bacteria growing on macroalgae and seagrasses, which underlines the likely importance of conserving natural macrophyte vegetation in marine and freshwater habitats to stabilize the pelagic ecological system (**Ichiro Imai**). But there are at least class-specific relations. In this context, **Kathryn Coyne**, showed us the algicide IRI-160, produced by bacteria, and which is active against dinoflagellates, particularly *Pfiesteria*, but not against non-dinoflagellate algae. The harmful effects of toxin-producing *Dinophysis cf ovum* in culture on its ciliate prey *Mesodinium rubrum* were shown in videos of *Dinophysis* cells secreting mucus aggregates and strands that trapped the ciliates as they swam. We saw *Mesodinium* cells which appeared to be trying to escape from their elastic trap, much as a fly tries to escape from a sticky spider's web. However, perhaps weakened by some toxins (ROS, PUFAs?) different from okadaic acid and dinophysistoxins, they are eventually captured by the *Dinophy-*

sis that suck out their contents with a feeding tube (myzocytosis) (**Luiz Mafra**). **Yolanda Pazos** showed how blooms of *Dinophysis* in the real world generally follow blooms of their prey, *Mesodinium*. **Marc Long** (honorary mention for student oral presentation) treated the impact of *Alexandrium minutum* culture filtrate on *Chaetoceros neogracile*. An allelopathic action on the diatom's thylakoids and cell membranes, apparently involving ROS, was observed very quickly (~5 min) after exposure.

Turning to ecology, **Beatriz Reguera's** presentation on fine-scale physical-biological interactions in *Dinophysis acuta* dynamics showed the short-term impact of upwelling on net growth due to dispersion, but also decreased division rates due to the effect of increased shear stress and mixing on the cells. **Raphael Siano** showed us how *Alexandrium minutum* has now invaded the Bay of Brest, France, to give regular blooms now of up to 40 million cells/L⁻¹, whereas back in 1990, the cyst record (PCR detection) shows that it was totally absent. *Vulcanodinium rugosa*, a pinnatoxin producer from a Mediterranean lagoon, has increased in all NW Mediterranean lagoons in the last decade, but in this case introduction by shellfish transfer is suspected. **Alejandro Clément** showed how changes in climate and ocean circulation appear to be changing not only the timing of blooms in southern Chile, but also the synergistic effect of blooms of the diatom *Leptocylindrus danicus* and the flagellate *Pseudochattonella*.

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Application of Molecular Technologies in HAB Research and Monitoring

Molecular approaches for HAB studies covered a vast number of issues, with special emphasis on the use of "omic" technologies to understand functional aspects of the biology and physiology of harmful species, as well as their detection in the field for monitoring purposes.

Genomic and transcriptomic studies on the domoic acid producer *Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata* (**Mariela Fer-**

rante) provided new information on the structure and evolution of diatom genomes, as well as the identification of a series of genes involved in sexual reproduction. The complexity of dinoflagellates genomes and their unique features was addressed on *Amphidinium carterae* (**Allan Place**), regarding the characterization of mechanisms that regulate translational processes involved in the synthesis of proteins (novel mRNA caps and eIF4Es). Diversity of Poliketide Synthase genes was shown in dinoflagellate genera such as *Ostreopsis* (**Arjun Verma**) and *Gambierdiscus* (**Gurjeet Kohli**). Saxitoxin production and its variability are known in several dinoflagellate species and genera. Genes involved in their synthesis have been explored (**Armando Mendoza-Flores**) to gain new insights on the evolutionary pathways through which these genes have been transferred from cyanobacteria to dinoflagellates. The proteomes of dinoflagellate species provide another approach to understand specific metabolic pathways and a novel technique (shotgun proteomics) for mapping the proteome of *Pyrodinium bahamense* was presented (**Bryan Subong**).

The study of population genetics and plankton communities was also highlighted during the conference by metagenomic studies on Japanese coastal waters (**Satochi Nagai**) and population genetic studies using microsatellites in benthic dinoflagellates (*Gambierdiscus caribaeus*; **Ingrid Sassenhagen**), *Pseudonitzschia multistriata* (**Marina Montresor**), *Cochlodinium polikrikoides* (**Satochi Nagai**), as well as RAD-TAG studies in freshwater systems (*Gonyostomum semen*; **Karin Rengefors**), to reveal geographical expansion and spatial differentiation among populations.

Studies of population genetic structure (SSU, V4rDNA) allowed the detection of entries of new species in the Gulf of Naples (**Adriana Zingone**). There are still some methodological issues (associated with DNA extraction, PCR efficiency and copy number per gene) to be improved for quantitation with metagenomics, but these are very helpful to unveil annual trends of plankton communities and their disturbances, as shown in Japanese coastal waters (**Nagai**) and in the Gulf of Naples (HTS metabarcoding; **Adriana Zingone**). Multiple studies also addressed the use

A nice take-home message from new generation molecular methods such as cell proteome analysis ([B.J. Jereza](#))

Jigsaw Puzzle

It's always the small pieces that make the big picture.

JIGSAW PUZZLE ANALOGY

kintsukuroi

(n.) (v. phr.) "to repair with gold"; the art of repairing pottery with gold or silver lacquer and understanding that the piece is more beautiful for having been broken

Cell proteome analysis, or how to use individual molecules, to make a beautiful picture about the nature of an organism, seen by the author as a jigsaw puzzle or "kintsukuroi".

of qPCR assays for HAB cells and cysts detection and enumeration (**Marcela Mora, Ruth Paterson, Raffaele Siano**), including the use of saxitoxin genes as a target (**Henna Savela, Claudia Piccini, Bruna Buch, Rendy Ruvindy**). Detection and prediction are two important issues for harvesting management that can be tackled by qPCR assays. In addition, we need more information on responsible genes, copy number per cell, changes in toxin production along the cell cycle, etc (**Ruth Paterson**).

Continuing a trend that started at least 20 years earlier, there was a strong set of talks on molecular assays for identifying and enumerating cells in monitoring programs. **Linda Medlin** updated participants on the status of phylochips now being used for multiple HAB species in five countries. Other highlights in this topic area were descriptions of the "Lab on a Chip", electrochemical detector (**Jahir Holguin**), and a fully automated, ship-based algal biosensor using electrochemical detection and phylochips (**Pim Sprong**). During a discussion at the end of the molecular detection session, it was clear that despite extensive development and testing by the research community and positive outcomes of that work, broad acceptance of molecular assays by monitoring and regulatory communities has not yet been achieved.

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Strong Focus in XVII ICHA Meeting for molecular tools for HAB monitoring
qPCR-based molecular assays ([R. Ruvindy, R. Paterson, M.I. Ferrante, ...](#))

- Targeting DNA instead of Toxins/Highly accurate/Cost-effective
- Rapid & Flexible:
 - Species determination
 - Saxitoxin gene

Detection + Prediction >>>> Harvesting Management

qPCR is not a «silver bullet» ([R. Paterson](#)) and needs more information on responsible genes, copy number per cell, changes in toxin production along the cell cycle (*Azadinium*, DA, etc)

Diagram about the application of molecular tools (qPCR) for monitoring purposes.

New HAB Technologies

A noteworthy feature of the ICHA conference in Florianopolis was the clear advancement in the use of *in situ* biosensors and autonomous vehicles for HAB studies. **Lisa Campbell** gave a plenary presentation about the use of the Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB), a submersible microscope capable of imaging thousands of cells every hour. She described how the IFCB is being used in Texas for early warning of HABs, resolution of phytoplankton community structure, and for long-term time series. Where the IFCB deployments in Texas were on dock or mobile (ship) platforms, **Mike Brosnahan** described an uncabled IFCB deployment with solar power, automated winch, and Wi-Fi for real-time profiling of the instrument and other contextual sensors. This yielded unprecedented insights of life cycle transi-

sitions underlying *Alexandrium* blooms. That talk also briefly described the co-deployment of an IFCB and ESP (Environmental Sample Processor), in which the high-frequency observations of the IFCB were used to guide the timing of the more limited sampling capabilities of the ESP – in that instance, used to measure toxin concentrations directly in the water.

Other instrument highlights included a plenary talk by **Raphe Kudela** on the use of multiple technologies for HAB studies (wave-powered profilers, AUVs, ESPs, IFCBs, and satellite remote sensing). Yet another talk in this context was by **Beatrix Siemerling** on the use of a satellite-guided glider in mapping of hydrography and chlorophyll in HAB monitoring and forecasting.

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Solar powered raft platform for uncabled IFCB deployment for *Alexandrium* and *Dinophysis* studies in Salt Pond, MA (USA). The submerged IFCB (and other instruments) is raised and lowered with an automated profiling winch. (Photo: M. Brosnahan)

Fish Killing Algae

Fish-killing algae were well covered at ICHA17 with one key note address, 10 talks, 9 posters, and a dedicated round table event. Special attention focused on the massive February-March 2016 Chilean *Pseudochattonella cf. verruculosa*/*Alexandrium catenella* bloom (**Alejandro Clement, Ximena Rojas, Leonardo Guzmán, Alejandra Aguilera, Fabiola Villanueva, Rodrigo Montes, Óscar Espinoza-González, Daniel Varela, Ximena Vivanco, Javier Paredes**) that killed 40,000 tonnes of salmon and trout. This event impacted on global markets and triggered social unrest. **Gustaaf Hallegraeff** (keynote speech) proposed that the unrelated flagellates *Chattonella*, *Heterosigma*, *Karenia*, *Cochlodinium* cause irreversible fish gill damage through the release of free fatty acids (EPA, DHA, OPA) which in synergism with reactive oxygen species generate labile lipid peroxidation products. Microelectrode ion flux estimation (MIFE) techniques are pursuing a fuller understanding of this process (**Jorge Mardones**). The role of HAB cell lysis (*Alexandrium catenella*), ROS (*Chattonella*), and strain variation in ichthyotoxicity was emphasized. Aeration increased toxicity by *Prymnesium* (**Edna Granéli**). Critically, none of these “ichthyotoxins” (with exception perhaps of brevetoxins produced by *Karenia brevis* and relatives) are of human health significance. This means that recently killed fish are still fit for human consumption. We therefore need more investment in fish farm harvest

techniques that allow fish to be kept alive while emergency harvesting operations can be instigated. In addition to airlift upwelling to dilute fish killing algal concentrations, the application of fine-ground clays which at environmentally acceptable concentrations can mop up ichthyotoxins offers considerable promise (**Andreas Seger**). Novel chemical structures were reported for metabolites from *Prymnesium* (B and C type prymnesins: **Per Juel Hansen, Aaron Andersen, Silas Rasmussen**) and *Karlodinium armiger* (karlotoxin congener termed karmitoxin: **Thomas Larsen, Sofie Binzer**). Karlotoxins disrupt lipid membranes via pore formation (**Allan Place**). Nighttime respiration by high biomass HAB events was demonstrated to drive anoxia in South Africa (**Grant Pitcher**).

Gustaaf Hallegraeff, University of Tasmania, Australia, Hallegraeff@utas.edu.au

Surveillance, management and mitigation

Two sessions considered the development of approaches for the role of surveillance, management and mitigation of HABs and their impacts.

In terms of surveillance many of the presented papers were related to the better understanding of how anthropogenic and/or climate drivers impacted HAB populations, with **Rajan Anbian** and **Kedong Yin** providing examples from Abu Dhabi and Hong Kong waters respectively.

The role of physical oceanography

was highlighted by **Robin Raine**. In the culmination of many years of work on *Dinophysis* in Irish waters, he was able to demonstrate the role of a tidal front between the tidally mixed Irish Sea and the thermally stratified Celtic sea in developing populations of *Dinophysis acuta* that are subsequently transported to locations of aquaculture production.

The management of HABs is increasingly likely to require a diversity of approaches. An example of this was illustrated in the presentation of **Mercy Borbor-Cordova** who described a collaborative partnership between interdisciplinary researchers, public health staff, and key local stakeholders, to achieve HAB risk assessment and management in relation to climate-ocean drivers in Ecuador.

Alexis Fisher (best ISSHA student presentation) presented a novel paper that demonstrated the potential role of winter chilling in governing *Alexandrium* excystment and hence offering new opportunities to predict the time and location of bloom initiation.

A number of the papers considered the issue of mitigation of toxins present in the water column. Some techniques are well known to the HAB community such as using clay, but the technique continues to be optimised with **Andreas Seger** demonstrating refinement of the technique with different materials and low clay concentrations that reduces both cost and environmental impact.

Other novel approaches reported were the use of compounds secreted by algicidal bacteria (**Eva Ternon**) to control dinoflagellates

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Toxins and toxicity

The monograph by Lassus et al., 2016, presented at the conference, made it clear that the largest uncertainties in the toxicity of algal metabolites reside in the ichthyotoxicity of many algae. This was also a theme at this conference. Significant progress was reported on metabolites from *Prymnesium parvum*; the chemical diversity in several strains from US and Europe was clarified with novel Prymnesin classes identified and chemically characterised in European

Co-deployment of IFCB (left) and ESP (right) in Salt Pond (USA) during 2016 *Alexandrium* bloom. (Photo: B. Keafer)

strains (**Kristian Nielsen, Silas Rasmussen, Per Juel Hansen**).

Investigation of recently isolated strains of the genera *Azadinium* and *Amphidoma* led to the identification of more than ten novel analogues of Azaspiracids (**Bernd Krock, Urban Tillmann**).

STX analogues in *G. catenatum* were reviewed and several reports on allelopathic compounds of *G. catenatum*, *Alexandrium* spp. and several other species were presented (**Mike Quilliam, Elise van Meerssche, Helene Hegaret, Chris Gobler, Stefanie Moorthi, Eva Ternon, Stefano Accaroni, Rui Wang, Mathias Chia, Kemal Ger, Lincoln MacKenzie, Renan Arruda, Anneke Purz**).

The combination of passive sampling and High Resolution Mass Spectrometry for algal and environmental metabolomics was presented as a break-through technology to investigate several aspects of toxin chemistry, including pinpointing towards novel toxins, chemogeography of toxins and spatio-temporal changes in the chemical profiles of coastal waters (**Phil Hess**).

Some progress was also reported in the evaluation of the toxicity of *Gam-*

bierdiscus species, especially Atlantic strains (**Francesco Pisapia**).

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Effects of HABs in shellfish and other higher trophic level organisms

Despite not causing an obvious harmful effect characteristic of the toxic syndrome, toxic harmful events can modify the susceptibility of bivalves to pathogens (**Celina Abi-Khalil**)

The HAB impacts observed on bivalves are not always due to the known toxins causing shellfish poisonings, such as PSP and DSP toxins, but can be associated to other un-characterized bioactive compounds produced by the toxin-producing species (**Elodie Borcier, Leila Basti**)

Intravenous Lipid Injection (ILE) increases the clearance of brevetoxins (PbTx) in turtle tissues and ameliorates symptoms of specimens exposed to toxic blooms of *Karenia brevis* (**Courtney Cocilova**)

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Homage to Edna Graneli

Edna Graneli, Professor Emeritus at the Linnaeus University, Kalmar, Sweden, and Guest Professor at the University of Lund, Sweden, has devoted her life to the ecology and ecophysiology of harmful microalgae and their blooms. First in Lund and later in Kalmar, she had PhD-students and visiting post-docs from different countries. Nevertheless, Edna never forgot her Brazilian origins, and she was a key person in the promotion of scientific exchanges and international cooperation with her fellow countrymen. For these reasons, Brazilian HAB experts wanted to thank Edna for her strong support to PhD students, some of them now with good academic positions in Brazil or elsewhere. Homage to Edna was done in a very Brazilian way: a barbecue and good samba music and dancing open to all participants in the 17 ICHA.

Edna Graneli with Luis Proena (top, photo M Schramm) and in the barbecue party with Proena and Paulo Salomon (bottom, photo P Salomon)

DEADLINE submission of manuscripts for the 17 ICHA Proceedings

The proceedings of the 17 ICHA conference will be published under the auspices of the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA). The complete proceedings will be published in digital format on the ISSHA web site, no later than 12 months after submission deadline, but reviewed, revised and accepted submissions will be uploaded prior to that as they are completed. Past conference proceedings can be accessed at www.issha.org

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From left to right and from top to bottom: 1-3, registration and icebreaker; 4-5, poster sessions; 6-7, socializing at the first day reception, including a "Macarena" dance. All photos by M Schramm, except 4 (Yolanda Pazos) and 6 (Don Anderson)

Bloom of *Vulcanodinium rugosum* linked to skin lesions in Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba

Fig. 1. Map of Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba and location of sampling stations. The arrow indicates the area where *V. rugosum* bloomed in summer 2015.

Vulcanodinium rugosum is a pinnatoxin-producing benthic dinoflagellate recently described from the Mediterranean [1, 2]. Pinnatoxins are included in the group of lipophilic “fast-acting toxins” (FAT) due to the strong toxicity observed in mouse bioassay via intraperitoneal injection [3]. Extracts of *V. rugosum* showed cytotoxicity and genotoxicity activities against cell lines derived from the nervous system and intestine [4]. To date, there is no evidence for human intoxication by shellfish contaminated with pinnatoxins [5]. The presence of *V. rugosum* has also been documented from Australia, China, Japan, Hawaii, Mexican Pacific and New Zealand [6].

During summer 2015, between 23 and 26 July, around 60 cases (most of them children) of skin lesions were recorded from some popular beaches in Cienfuegos Bay, a semi-enclosed embayment with estuarine characteristics from central-southern Cuba (Fig. 1)[7]. The affected people showed symptoms quite different from those caused by coelenterates which are very frequent in summer and known in Cuba as “Caribe”. The skin lesions eventually got

infected and purulent and had to be treated with antibiotics. Analyses were carried out at the Cienfuegos Provincial Health, Epidemiology and Microbiology Centre and at the Centre for Environmental Studies (CEAC) and the possibility of bacterial infection or chemical pollution behind the skin lesions was discarded. Health authorities swiftly enforced beaches closures to the public. This caused social alarm and affected local tourism [7].

Microbiological analyses (for viruses and bacteria) carried out by the Epidemiological Center from Cienfuegos Province (CPHE) gave negative results. Sub-surface water samples for phytoplankton analysis were collected from the beaches

and fixed with Lugol’s iodine. Live specimens were observed under a light microscope Laborlux, Leica-Leitz with phase contrast, and micrographs taken. For scanning electron microscopy, the Lugol’s-fixed material was rinsed with distilled water, dehydrated in an ethanol series, critical-point dried, and finally coated with gold.

Reddish-brown long discontinuous patches, mainly 3-6 m nearshore, were observed at the beaches affected by the dermatitis outbreak. The extent of this intense water discoloration was about 1 km. Patches were located near the bottom during the morning and moved to the surface during mid-day, a behavioural pattern common to benthic species (Fig. 2). The bloom persisted for around two months, until 20 September 2015.

Microscopic observations revealed the presence of a *Vulcanodinium rugosum* bloom. Some typical features of this peridinoid dinoflagellate, such as the distinctive apical pore complex on the motile cells, through which mucilaginous material is extruded, were corroborated. All plates were ornamented with numerous circular tricho-

cyst pores and prominent longitudinal ridges, the presence of a narrow and invaginated 1’ plate and the production of abundant spherical cyst-like cells enclosed in a gelatinous matrix. (Figs. 3-4). Ongoing studies will be performed on their toxicology and genetic characterization.

V. rugosum formed an almost monospecific bloom during the first 20 days, when other dinoflagellates and diatoms, including several bloom-forming species, such as *Dinophysis caudata*, *Peridinium quinquecorne*, *Prorocentrum micans*, *Tripos furca* and *T. trichoceros*, co-occurred in the samples in very low concentrations.

For the Western Atlantic, *V. rugosum* has only been reported in ship’s ballast water samples from Tampa, USA [8]. To our knowledge, the occurrence of *V. rugosum* in a natural environment from Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba, represents the first report of this species for the Caribbean region and for the Western Atlantic.

Environmental conditions during late July 2015 in Cienfuegos Bay – high salinity (34-36), water temperature above 30°C and strong irradiance – were favourable for dinoflagellate blooms. In addition, the semi-enclosed

Fig. 2. Intense water discoloration due to the bloom of *V. rugosum* from the beaches of Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba. The red line indicates the length of the patch.

Fig. 3. Light microscopy micrographs of *V. rugosum* from Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba. A. Nonmotile spherical cells encased in a gelatinous matrix. B. Nonmotile spherical cells. C-D. Motile cells showing the distinct apical pore complex of the species.

nature of Cienfuegos Bay promotes the development and retention of blooms. The occurrence of *V. rugosum* coincided with the summer-rainy season. This season is characterized by decreasing salinity values and increased water turbulence, leading to resuspension of a high abundance of estuarine diatoms and chlorophyceans in the bay [9]. Nevertheless, 2015 was extremely dry and the hottest of the last 64 years in Cuba [10]. These extreme weather conditions (high salinity, temperature, irradiance and water residence times) appeared to be optimal for bloom-forming dinoflagellates.

Predictions indicate that the Cuban climate will be affected by warming and drought periods, which seems appropriate for the development of harmful/toxic blooms. This relation between weather conditions and HABs is valuable information to improve national capabilities to predict HABs in Cuban embayments. Recent harmful algal blooms, including fish-killing blooms of *Cochlodinium polykrikoides*, have been recorded in Cienfuegos and Santiago de Cuba bays, always during hot and dry periods. These blooms caused significant damage to the marine fauna. [11].

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Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of *V. rugosum* from Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba. A. Epitheca of a motile cell in ventral view showing the large pore plate (Po). B. Ventral view of a motile cell showing the narrow 1' plate and the girdle displacement. C. Two motile cells linked together by the mucus exudated through the apical pore complex.

Ability of giant clams to bio-accumulate ciguatoxins from *Gambierdiscus* cells

Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (CFP) is a seafood poisoning classically related to the consumption of tropical coral reef fish contaminated with ciguatoxins (CTXs). These polyether neurotoxins are produced by dinoflagellates in the genus *Gambierdiscus* [1]. Pacific Island Countries and Territories (PICTs) communities, who are dependent on seafood for their subsistence but also for fishery and tourism industries, are among the populations most affected by CFP worldwide [2]. In these countries, marine invertebrates such as giant clams also constitute highly prized food resources. Unfortunately, in several of these PICTs such as French Polynesia, New-Caledonia, Cook Islands and Republic of Vanuatu, atypical ciguatera-like poisonings incidents following the consumption of giant clams *Tridacna maxima* (Fig. 1) have been reported in recent years [3,4]. As an example, in French Polynesia, official reports of these atypical forms of poisonings following the consumption of various marine invertebrates including *Tridacna maxima* (giant clam) [4], *Tripneustes gratilla* (sea urchin) [5], and *Tectus niloticus* (gastropod) [6] exist, although they represent less than 10 cases/year versus an average of 300 fish poisoning

cases officially reported annually (www.ciguatera-online.com). These statistics about poisonings triggered by consumption of marine invertebrates may however be largely underestimated, as marine invertebrate meals are often omitted in clinical reports whereas fish meals are incriminated [5]. During these ciguatera-like intoxications, classical symptoms of CFP are observed (gastrointestinal disorders, reversal of hot and cold sensations, itching, paresthesia, asthenia, muscular pain, dizziness), in addition to atypical symptoms (alteration of the taste, burning sensation on the tongue and the throat, paralysis) [4], suggesting the involvement of several toxin families, including CTX-like toxins.

Giant clams are bivalve molluscs capable of filtering seawater and retaining particles that are in suspension in the water column such as microalgal cells. *Gambierdiscus* cells have a tythropelagic life style, meaning that this benthic dinoflagellate can temporarily become free-swimming in the water column, especially in high-energy environments. In the process, senescent *Gambierdiscus* cells can release dissolved CTXs in the surrounding water. It is thus likely that giant clams living in areas contaminat-

ed with toxic *Gambierdiscus* blooms can potentially accumulate CTXs in their tissues, either by direct ingestion of toxic *Gambierdiscus* cells dispersed in the water column, or by filtration of seawater containing dissolved CTXs. To test this hypothesis and to assess the ability of giant clams to bioaccumulate CTXs upon an episodic exposure to high densities of *Gambierdiscus* cells, *ex situ* contamination experiments of giant clams with *in vitro* cultures of *Gambierdiscus* strains were conducted (Fig. 2) [7].

Giant clams were exposed for 48 h to live cells or lyzed cells homogenates of *Gambierdiscus*, to mimic natural exposure to free-swimming *Gambierdiscus* cells and dissolved CTXs, respectively. Two distinct strains were used: (i) *G. polynesiensis* TB92, a highly toxic strain containing approximately 5.83 ± 0.85 pg P-CTX-3C equiv. cell⁻¹; and (ii) *G. toxicus* HIT0, a strain 2,850-fold less toxic than TB92, containing approximately $2.05 \pm 1.16 \times 10^{-3}$ pg P-CTX-3C equiv. cell⁻¹. Exposure experiments were conducted at an overall concentration of 150 cells mL⁻¹, equivalent to 0.86 µg P-CTX-3C equiv. L⁻¹ and 0.31×10^{-3} µg P-CTX-3C equiv. L⁻¹ in the case of TB92 and HIT0 strains respectively. The presence of CTXs congeners in giant clams tissues was further assessed using the mouse neuroblastoma cell-based assay (CBAN2a). Results showed that giant clams exposed to either live cells or lyzed cells homogenates of TB92 were able to bio-accumulate similar levels of toxins, *i.e.* 2.92 ± 1.03 and 3.28 ± 1.37 ng P-CTX-3C equiv. g⁻¹ flesh (wet weight) respectively (Table 1). These concentrations are well above the safety limit of 0.01 ppb P-CTX-1B (or 0.02 ppb P-CTX-3C) recommended for human consumption in the Pacific region [8]. In contrast, control animals (no exposition to *Gambierdiscus* cells) and giant clams exposed to cells of the weakly toxic strain HIT0 were found to be free of toxins (Table 1), suggesting that the nature, the risk of contamination of these bivalves is established only in the presence of highly toxic blooms of *Gambierdiscus*. Liquid chromatography mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) analyses confirmed CBAN2a results and revealed that P-CTX-3B was the major CTX congener retained in the tissues of giant clams fed with TB92 cells.

Fig. 1. Giant clam (*Tridacna maxima*). © M. Roué.

Fig. 2. Ex situ contamination experiment: giant clams were first acclimated in experimental tanks containing 20 L of seawater (A) and further exposed to *in vitro* cultures of *Gambierdiscus* spp. (B-C). © M. Roué (A, B); © ILM (C).

The results of this study [7] provide evidence of the bioaccumulation of CTXs from *Gambierdiscus* cells in giant clams and thus confirm that these molluscs, which are part of the diet of many populations in PICTs, can actually constitute another pathway in ciguatera poisonings in areas where toxic *Gambierdiscus* populations are endemic.

These findings highlight the need for an improved global strategy on ciguatera risk assessment and management programs currently on-going in PICTs. These programs, so far limited to the survey of lagoon fish, should also take into account all major seafood resources consumed within island communities, including those, such as giant clams, commonly regarded as being at low risk of ciguatera.

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Table 1. Estimation of toxin contents in giant clams exposed to live cells or lyzed cells homogenates of *Gambierdiscus*, using CBA-N2a. ND: not detectable.

Condition of exposure	Strain	Giant clams per tank	Giant clams total wet weight (g)	Toxin content ± SD (ng P-CTX-3C equiv g ⁻¹ wet weight of flesh)
Lyzed cells	control	3	213	ND
	HIT0	3	180	ND
	TB92, tank 1	3	176	3.74 ± 0.26
	TB92, tank 2	3	159	4.96 ± 0.58
	TB92, tank 3	3	137	2.02 ± 0.10
	TB92, average of tanks 1-3	9	157	3.58 ± 1.32
Live cells	control	2	95	ND
	HIT0	3	172	ND
	TB92, tank 1	3	170	3.94 ± 1.21
	TB92, tank 2	3	224	2.48 ± 0.29
	TB92, tank 3	3	197	2.34 ± 0.54
	TB92, average of tanks 1-3	9	197	2.92 ± 1.03

Bloom of *Gambierdiscus caribaeus* in the temperate-subtropical waters of El Hierro, Canary Islands (North East Atlantic)

Fig. 1. Shaded relief image of El Hierro (GRAFCAN), Canary Islands. Location of the study area in La Restinga.

The Canary Archipelago (Fig. 1) is located in the southern limit of the temperate Northern Atlantic (28°06'N, 15°24'W) and together with the archipelagos of Azores, Madeira, Selvagens and Cape Verde, is part of a unique biogeographical region known as Macaronesia. El Hierro is the southernmost, smallest and most isolated island of the Canary archipelago and has been declared a UNESCO Biosphere Reserve.

The first record of a harmful algal bloom in the Canary Archipelago occurred quite recently, in August 2004, when a bloom of the planktonic cyanobacteria *Trichodesmium erythraeum* Ehrenberg ex Gomont developed along the coasts of Lanzarote, Fuerteventura, Gran Canaria and Tenerife [1]. In January, this same year, an outbreak of Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (CFP) was docu-

mented for the first time in the Canary Islands, after the ingestion of a locally captured amberjack (*Seriola rivoliana* Valenciennes 1833) [2]. This event was quite unexpected since, by then, the Canary Islands were considered outside the recognised endemic area for CFP and the causative species (*Gambierdiscus* spp.) had not been reported for the region.

The presence of *Gambierdiscus* in the archipelago was first reported in November 2004, at the XI International Conference on Harmful Algae (Cape Town, South Africa), from samples collected in March of the same year on the northern coast of Tenerife [3,4]. Since then, five toxic species of *Gambierdiscus* have been reported for the Canary Islands, including two newly erected species for science, *G. excentricus* S. Fraga and *G. silvae* S. Fraga & F. Rodríguez [4-6]. Until now, most work on *Gambierdiscus* has resulted from opportunistic samples and short sampling expeditions, from which cells have been isolated and cultured under laboratory conditions for further taxonomical and toxicological studies. High densities have never been reported.

In the third week of October 2016, the international subaquatic photography contest Open FotoSub took place in La Restinga – Mar de las Calmas, El Hierro, an ecosystem with a high biodiversity, declared as a protected marine reserve. When diving, some of the participants were intrigued by the presence of a weird-looking brownish matt covering the sea bottom (Fig. 2). To investigate these observations, samples of the macroalgae *Padina pavonica* (Linnaeus) Thivy, *Dictyota* spp. and *Halopteris scoparia* (Linnaeus) Sauvageau were collected, by snorkelling (ca. 2m depth), using

plastic bags, from 5 sampling sites in the harbour of La Restinga (27° 37,5' N 17° 59' 5" W). Samples were vigorously shaken and the water suspension was collected in stoppered tubes for further analysis in the laboratory. At the time of sampling water temperature was 25°C and salinity 36.8.

The epiphytic assemblages were investigated by light microscopy (Leica DM6000B) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) (JEOL JSM-6380LV). For plate tabulation description of *Gambierdiscus* we followed the nomenclature according to [3]. Cells were measured from SEM images using SEM Control User Interface v.7.11A by JEOL. Only cells that were clearly in apical and antapical view, were measured.

Sample observation revealed *Gambierdiscus* spp. was the only dinoflagellate present in the recovered epiphytic community (Fig. 3). A diverse diatom flora co-occurred with *Gambierdiscus* spp., namely species of the genera *Actinocyclus*, *Achnanthes*, *Amphora*, *Nitzschia* and *Pleurosigma* (Fig. 3). In one sample of *H. scoparia* the concentration of *Gambierdiscus* spp. was estimated, reaching more than 10⁴ cells g⁻¹ wet weight. This value is close to some of the maximal concentrations referred for other species of *Gambierdiscus* in CFP affected areas [7].

All cells of *Gambierdiscus* analysed were antero-posteriorly compressed and round to slightly oval shaped in apical view. The thecal surface was smooth with evenly distributed round pores. Observation by calcofluor staining and SEM revealed an almost centrally located Po (slight ventral displacement) with a fish-hook like slit, surrounded by a row of pores, in some areas with 2 rows (Fig. 4). The chloroplasts were golden-brown. The dorso-ventral depth (DV) range was 71.4-82.8µm (n=7) and the width (W) range 62.2-82.9µm, with a mean DV/W ratio of 1.1±0.11. In the episome (Fig. 4), plate 2' was the biggest apical plate and varied from rectangular to hatched-shaped with the ratio between the suture length of 2'/1" and 2'/3" ranging between 0.63 and 1.0 (mean=0.84±0.14, n=9). Plate 3' was pentagonal and small relative to 2'. Plate 4' and plate 3" were symmetrical. Plate 1' was very narrow and small, not visible in apical view but clearly visible in ventral view (Fig. 5). Specimens observed

Fig. 2. *Gambierdiscus* mats smothering a cnidarian *Halecium* sp. colony (courtesy L. Moro). Inset: detail showing cells of *Gambierdiscus* spp.

Fig. 3. SEM micrograph of epiphytic community (a. *G. caribaeus*; b. *Pleurosigma* sp.; *Actinocyclus* sp.).

Fig. 4. *Gambierdiscus caribaeus*, apical view with plate tabulation (SEM).

Fig. 5. *Gambierdiscus caribaeus*, ventral view, with identification of sulcal plates (SEM).

Fig. 6. *Gambierdiscus caribaeus*, antapical view showing the broad 2''' plate (SEM).

in antapical view were characterized by a broad 2''' plate, almost symmetrical, with a pointed dorsal end (Fig. 6). Length of plate 2''' ranged between 45.3 and 51.8µm (mean=48.9±2.62, n=5). Plate 1''' contacted plates 1'', 2'' and 2'''. All specimens observed in antapical view showed the same tabulation. The hyposome tabulation, combined with surface characteristics and cell morphology, is in good agreement with the original description of *Gambierdiscus caribaeus* Vandersea, Litaker, M.A.Faust, Kibler, W.C.Holland & P.A.Tester [7], a species recently reported from the Canary Islands [6]. Although in some of the studied specimens the diagnostic criteria of the episome showed some variability, several specimens agreed well with the original description of *G. caribaeus* [8] (Figs 4-6). This, combined with the unambiguous tabulation of the

hyposome, suggests *G. caribaeus* was the dominant species in the El Hierro bloom. The observed variability on the episome may either correspond to natural intra-specific variability or indicate that cryptic species of *Gambierdiscus* were present. Ongoing genetic characterization of the original bloom samples and of clonal isolates will allow us to clarify the mono- versus pluri-specific nature of the El Hierro bloom.

The high concentrations of *Gambierdiscus* spp., reported here from La Restinga, suggest that the Ciguatera outbreaks reported for the Canary Archipelago and other Macaronesia islands, in the last two decades, may result from locally toxified fish and not from long-distance migration of fish from other affected areas.

The frequency of HABs in the Canary Islands has been increasing since

the first reported event in 2004. BEA (Banco Español de Algas), in cooperation with the regional environmental authorities (Viceconsejería de Medio Ambiente del Gobierno de Canarias), has been monitoring and studying these events since then. Blooms are quite diverse and include the planktonic species *Trichodesmium erythraeum* (August 2004 and 2011) and *Noctiluca scintillans* (Macartney) Kofoid & Swezy (March 2012 and May 2016) [9] and the benthic toxic species *Lyngbya majuscula* Harvey ex Gomont (2010-present) [10] which has a dramatic impact in regional seagrass meadows of *Cymodocea nodosa* (Ucria) Ascherson. Human mediated global changes, such as ocean warming, may be driving the regional increase in HABs. The herein reported bloom of the

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Sand-lance, a key PSP-toxins vector in the Aleutian Pribilof Islands

Fig. 1: Map of the Aleutian Pribilof Islands in the Bering Sea, off Alaska

The Aleutian Pribilof Islands Association, Inc. (APIA) is a tribal consortium serving Alaska's thirteen Aleut Tribes. APIA's purpose is: to promote the overall economic, social, and cultural development of the Aleutian and Pribilof Islands Region; to help Tribes to protect public health and the environment; and to encourage sustainable management of the natural resources upon which the Aleut people depend. Environmental programs are located within APIA's Health Department. The specific mission of this department is achieving safe, healthy and sustainable communities.

The APIA harmful algal bloom program goals and objectives meet evolving needs by the Tribes to understand the risks of illness and death and the associated shifts in the marine ecosystems from harmful algal blooms.

Scientists from the Aleutian Pribilof Islands Association (APIA), off Alaska, USA (Fig. 1), have been working with governmental institutions and university researchers since 2006 to study paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) events in the region. Their research may help to determine the causes of near extinction of some of Gulf of Alaska top predators, such as sea otters and sea lions, and the decline of other predator populations. Studies of food, predation and disease have not satisfactorily resolved the reasons for these declining populations

and one hypothesis under investigation is that wide-spread PSP toxins (PST), transferred through the food web, may be partially responsible.

Every year coastal Alaska suffers from blooms of the PST producer *Alexandrium* spp. (Fig. 2a). PSP toxins can sicken wildlife and people and both can die if PST concentrations are high enough. The most common reason peo-

ple get sick is from eating PST-contaminated shellfish (mussels, clams and scallops) which filter the toxic *Alexandrium* sp. from the water column. Zooplankton, including copepods, may also eat *Alexandrium* cells and concentrate their toxins.

Sand lance, also known as "sand eels" or "needle fish", gets its name from its slender body and pointed snout (Fig.2b). Sand lance primarily feeds on copepods and may become toxic with PST transferred by copepods. Many of the marine predators in the North Pacific Ocean depend upon sand lance as an important food source. This fish is a highly caloric food due to its high content in lipids (fats), and contain many important nutrients. Some of the predators that feed on sand lance are whales, sea lions, seals, sea otters, marine birds, and fish including salmon and halibut. PST affect the vertebrates central nervous system; when sand lance become contaminated with PST they may lose their ability to swim and may not be able to avoid predators. In Alaska's Taiyasanaka Harbor, Dungeness crab became so contaminated from eating dead PST-contaminated sand lance and mussels that they were toxic enough to sicken people when consumed. Sea birds have also been reported to have died on Kodiak Island and in the Aleu-

Fig. 2. Top: *Alexandrium* paired cell; bottom: a sand lance.

tian Islands from eating contaminated sand lance.

Yukon king salmon also eat PST-contaminated sand lance when reared in coastal waters. Dead seabirds washed up on the beach may have been killed by eating contaminated sand lance. The way to find it out is to check the bird's crop, to see if the bird ate sand lance, and test the toxicity in the fish.

WARNING: We need your help! Contact APIA senior scientist if you find sick acting or dead sand lance on the beach or in shallow water. You can handle the sand lance without risk of getting sick, but don't eat any dead or sick sand lance. If you find dead or dying sand lance, collect 5 specimens, put them in a Ziplock bag, label it with your name, location collected and date, freeze and contact: Bruce Wright at 907-222-4260 or brucew@apiai.org (Fig. 3).

More information at: <http://environmentalaska.us/psp-harmful-algal-blooms>

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WANTED: DEAD

Sand Lance AKA Needle Fish AKA Sand Eels

Sand lance can become contaminated with paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) and become sick or die. Sea lions, seals, sea otters, marine birds and salmon that eat these toxic sand lance can die too.

If you find dead or dying sand lance: collect 5, put in a Ziplock, label with your name, location collected and date, freeze and contact: Bruce Wright at 907-222-4260 or brucew@apiai.org for shipping instructions.

Fig. 3: Flyer asking for citizen's collaboration with the sand lance project.

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tropical species *G. caribaeus* in El Hierro, may represent additional evidence for the poleward shift of environmental conditions favouring the proliferation of warm water species at higher latitudes [11].

We are grateful to Leopoldo Moro for the photo of *Halecium* sp. and to Julia Pérez de Paz from Departamento de Biología Reproductiva y Micro-Morfología, Jardín Botánico Canario "Viera y Clavijo" for access to SEM facilities. A. Amorim acknowledges Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) for funding through grant SFRH/BSAB/127851/2016 and strategic project UID/MAR/04292/2013.

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Massive bloom of *Triplos furca* in Luanda Bay, Angola

Fig. 1. Location of Ponte Cais (red dot) 8°46.74" S; 13°14.75" E, in Luanda Bay.

On August 12th, 2016, waters in the entry area of Baía de Luanda, Angola, were discoloured brown. Three days later this discolouration was also observed at Ponte Cais de Carvão (Fig 1), close to the National Fishery Research Institute (INIP). Staff from INIP, Department of Oceanography and Marine Health Ecosystem, promptly collected water samples and measured environmental parameters (temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen) *in situ* to determine if the cause of the discolouration was due to a microalgal bloom.

Surface water samples were collected and fixed with a formalin (2%) solution. Microplankton identification and counts were conducted using a Zeiss Axiovert 200 inverted microscope using the Utermöhl method [1].

Oxygen levels (that in cold waters can reach values up to 10 mL L⁻¹)

Fig. 2. Brownish water discoloration from a *Triplos furca* bloom.

dropped from 7 to 2 mL L⁻¹ during the bloom although high values were recorded at surface on the first day of bloom related to photosynthesis. Temperature (13°C) and salinity (35.5) remained constant and pH varied from 7.4 to 8.5 [2].

Sample analyses confirmed the occurrence of a massive dinoflagellate bloom. The dominant species was *Triplos furca* (Fig. 2) with a density of 6.7×10^5 cells L⁻¹ (Fig. 3) Densities of this species $>10^5$ cells L⁻¹ have been defined as a bloom in previous studies. Chlorophyll *a* reached values of 12.65 µg L⁻¹ and dropped to 0.17 µg L⁻¹ when the bloom was over.

Triplos furca has been classified as a potentially noxious microalgae species

by the IOC of UNESCO. Even though is not classified as a toxin producer, the occurrence of massive blooms of this species may cause fish kills due to occlusion of the fish branchia, a situation that can also reduce the fish condition factor. This effect is more noticeable in plankton feeding *Sardinella* (Clupeidae family). Nevertheless, there was no visible fish mortality associated with this bloom in Luanda Bay. In contrast, in August-September 2010, a brownish discolouration was also observed in the water, caused by another dinoflagellate bloom where the dominant species was *Prorocentrum micans* (6×10^5 cells L⁻¹). In that bloom, *Triplos furca* (4.4×10^4 cells L⁻¹) was a co-occurring species and there was a mass mortality of fish at Luanda Bay. The cause of this mortality has not been identified.

Acknowledgements

To all the technicians involved in the investigation of this incident at the Department of Oceanography and Health of the Marine Ecosystem of the National Institute of Fisheries Research.

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Fig. 3. Contribution of the dominant phytoplankton species during the bloom

Water discoloration, fish kills and the occurrence of a multispecific dinoflagellate bloom off Kodikkal, southwest coast of India

Fig. 1. Map of the study area in Southwestern Indian coastal waters.

Conspicuous surface water discoloration and fish mortality were reported by fishermen along the northern coast of Kerala, especially off Kodikkal (11°28'43"N & 75°36'10"E), southwest India, from 24 to 26 August 2015 (Fig. 1). Patches spread over an area of about 2 km off the coast. Surface water samples revealed they were dominated by dinoflagellates *Dinophysis caudata* (1.5×10^4 cells L⁻¹) and *Tripos massiliensis* (formerly *Ceratium massiliense*) (1.1×10^4 cells L⁻¹) (Fig. 2).

Other phytoplankton species that contributed to the bloom included *Tripos trichoceros* (formerly *Ceratium trichoceros*), *Nitzschia closterium*, *Proboscia alata*, *Noctiluca scintillans*, *Pseudo-nitzschia cf. seriata* and *Thalassiosira*

sp. [1-4]. Surface chlorophyll *a* concentration was 17.58 µg L⁻¹, dissolved oxygen 5.47 mg L⁻¹ [5]. Nutrient concentrations recorded in the bloom area were: nitrate 0.148 µmol L⁻¹ [6], nitrite 0.039 µmol L⁻¹, phosphate 0.245 µmol L⁻¹ and silicate 1.617 µmol L⁻¹.

Nevertheless, the fish killing mechanism was not clarified.

The potentially toxic dinoflagellate, *Dinophysis caudata*, has been previously observed in west Indian waters [7-8]. An exceptional bloom of this species was reported along the southeast coast in 1994 [9].

This is the first report of a bloom involving *Dinophysis* along the southwest coast of India. The species forming the bloom are usually present offshore and their presence in coastal waters might be due to the advection of oceanic water. The southwest coast of India, especially the Malabar coast, is highly vulnerable to algal blooms. Seasonal upwelling and monsoonal forcing, which result in nutrient-enriched waters, followed by

advective processes, provide a competitive edge for the formation of phytoplankton blooms.

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Fig. 2. Micrographs of *Dinophysis caudata* field populations during the bloom event: a) Single cell of *D. caudata*; b) sample with dominance of *D. caudata*; c) isolated cells of *D. caudata* within a population dominated by *Tripos massiliense*.

Azadinium Research Survey aboard the Celtic Voyager completed successfully

Fig. 1. Map of sampling stations visited during the Azadinium Research Survey

Ongoing research to understand the distribution and mechanism of *Azadinium* species and the production of Azaspiracid has been a major focus of research scientists at the Irish Marine Institute for several years. A survey aboard the Research Vessel *Celtic Voyager* was carried out in August along the south and western coasts to repeat a similar survey carried out in 2012 (Fig. 1). This recent survey generated samples from 56 stations along the track helping us to understand how the presence of *Azadinium* can result in

shellfish toxicity that causes annual closures and economic hardship to many shellfish farmers and fishermen around the coast. In addition the survey took sediments for benthos analysis from 20 stations to add to the existing monitoring programmes in the MI and to look for the presence of interesting cyst stages. The survey completed 5 transects perpendicular to the coast far out onto the continental shelf making vertical profiles through the water to visualise the physical oceanography and collect depth samples. Underway sampling was

carried out between transects to collect phytoplankton, and an ADCP (Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler) was deployed on the seabed in Killary Harbour which will continue to measure high resolution current speed and direction for the next couple of months.

Altogether, over 1000 samples were collected and returned to the lab for analysis of various types including toxin analysis and PCR analyses for the presence of the *Azadinium* genus and species within. Initial results of this PCR analysis indicate that 2016 was quite different to 2012. The presence of *Azadinium* was very low this year in contrast to 2012 when it was found at most stations. This ties in well with the observations of toxins in the shellfish, 2012 being a year where AZA caused lots of closures to shellfish production areas while AZA was not a problem in 2016, a year which was more dominated by *Dinophysis* and DSP toxicity in the South West of the country. The water profiles from both years indicated a broadly similar salinity structure but slightly warmer surface waters in 2016. There was a well-developed pycnocline present both years between approximately 20-30 metres depth. Analysis of the samples will continue to look in particular for the presence of cysts and to build up our knowledge of why some years are more dominated by Azaspiracid toxins than others. Further surveys are planned in 2017 and 2018 to continue to build up our data on the occurrence of this interesting and novel HAB.

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Azadinium spinosum (photo Urban Tilmann)

MARBioFEED – enhanced biorefining methods for the production of marine biotoxins and microalgae fish feed

MARBioFEED is a three year project supported by the First Call for Transnational Research Projects within the Marine Biotechnology ERA-NET, involving partners from Ireland (Marine Institute), Norway (Norwegian Veterinary Institute), Spain (Spanish Oceanographic Institute and Neoalgae) and Canada (National Research Council).

Project background and aims

The quality assurance of fish and shellfish for human consumption is of paramount importance in ensuring the marketability of products from this expanding and predominantly rural sector. The global demand for fish is increasing due to an expanding population and the awareness that fish is a healthy food source. With increased pressure on land-based agriculture due to climate change, the potential for sustainable marine sourced food is growing. The industry and regulators rely heavily on analytical reference materials to guarantee safety for human health. This project will involve large-scale algal biotechnology for the production of value added products (marine biotoxin reference materials and fish feed).

Large scale purification of marine biotoxins using enhanced biorefining methods for low cost reference materials and research

Most shellfish production sites in the EU are prone to closures due to the accumulation of biotoxins, produced by certain phytoplankton. Over 26 EU-regulated toxins currently require statutory monitoring and many more are being discovered. This places pressure on monitoring laboratories and researchers to develop and produce reference materials that allow for their analysis in a cheap, timely and effective way, while still maintaining the highest standards. The importance of aquaculture industries to peripheral European regions cannot be overstated. Most shellfish producing countries, including Ireland, Norway and Spain have implemented

programmes to monitor both toxic algae and shellfish, potentially exposed to these microalgae, as a result of legislative requirements.

One element of the project will focus on isolation of large quantities of biotoxins to produce reference materials for a range of toxins to safeguard the sustainability and cost effectiveness of monitoring programmes, thereby supporting the long term expansion and viability of the shellfish industry. Further supplies of purified toxins will be commercially available at low cost for

researchers in areas such as marine environment, toxicology, pharmacology, assay development, mode of action, mitigation, etc. Sourcing of naturally contaminated shellfish, bulk algal culturing, harvesting of algal blooms *in situ* and enzymatic conversions will be performed to source toxins of importance. The development and use of novel immunoaffinity and polymeric columns will be investigated to enhance purification efficiencies to reduce cost and increase economic viability.

Nutritious and sustainable microalgal biomass and shellfish for fish feed

Manufactured feeds are an important part of modern commercial aquaculture, providing the balanced nutrition needed by farmed fish. Fish feed is made, in part, from fishmeal and fish-concentrated products requiring much larger volumes of small ocean fish (such as anchovies, herring and sardines). Efforts are now being made to shift fish feed away from marine sources due to rising costs, reduced availability and environmental/sustainability issues. Research in this area is currently in its infancy and there is huge potential for innovative technologies and development in this field.

The project aims to support the efforts being made to produce more sustainable, highly nutritious but low cost feed for fish. Microalgae provide an excellent alternative to fishmeal, having exceptional nutritional value with high contents of essential amino acids and lipids. There is strong need to exploit the great potential offered by this diverse group of organisms. Medium/small scale culturing of microalgae will be performed to determine optimum growth and nutrition with subsequent transfer of technologies developed to large scale culturing using 1,200 L photobioreactors. Harvested materials can then be formulated to produce fish feed.

Mussels unsuitable for human consumption also offer another environmentally friendly alternative to

fishmeal, but require research to evaluate the potential effects of the algal toxins they sometimes contain, both on farmed fish and on fish consumers. Work on farmed salmon in Norway has highlighted the need for studies to be performed on the chronic effects of algal toxins on fish health, in addition to possible exposure to humans through the food chain. Such studies require substantial amounts of purified toxins which currently are too costly to purchase at current market prices and are unavailable in the required amounts.

For further information please contact the project co-ordinator Jane Kilcoyne.

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ISSHA'S CORNER

Conference News

Bonjir (Bom dia), *Floripa!* (Hello, Florianopolis!)

This was the greeting in Portuguese for the attendees of the 17th International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA2016) in Florianopolis, Brazil, the first ever conference to be held in South America. The conference, from 9-14 October 2016, featured 350 participants from 35 countries who presented 145 talks and 210 posters. A series of “ignite” talks (2 sessions of 10 presentations each) were a great way for poster presenters to give a 5-minute introduction to their topics. Among the submitted papers, 355 were selected for presentation in 14 different topic areas. Considering all the works submitted, the total number of authors participating in the event reached about 1500, representing 438 institutions around the world. We extend our sincere thanks to Luis Proença, the local and international organizing committees, and the staff at the *Federal Institute of Santa Catarina*, IFSC for making the conference a great success. We thoroughly enjoyed the excellent scientific program, the conference locale including lovely historical Florianopolis and its fantastic seafood, and the Wednesday afternoon tours that gave us a “taste” of the surrounding region. At the conference banquet, after enjoying the world-class local food and drink, we were treated to a samba dancing demonstration complete with accompanying troupe of drummers from the local *Escola de Samba*. It was hard to sit still and many of our colleagues joined together on the dance floor for a lively international party.

About 110 participants from 35 countries responded to a pool about the

17 ICHA and their satisfaction level. The score for the overall subjective evaluation was 8.25 over 10 and for the objective evaluation (26 questions), 4.25 over 5.

There were 36 applicants for the first ever *Student Speed Networking* mini-course, held on Sunday, October 9, led by mentors Vera Trainer and Lisa Campbell, Adriana Zingone and Marina Montresor and Mohammad Abdul Baki. Highlights were our discussion on the importance of networking and how to give an interesting and captivating *elevator speech* to colleagues. It was emphasized that it should take about 30 seconds to introduce yourself and your work by including a *hook* or something that captures your listener, and ending by summarizing where you are in your career and whether you are looking for a position. Students were encouraged to tell their listener when their presentation (poster or talk) would be given at the meeting. They rotated among 4 tables and while practicing their speeches, had the opportunity also to get to know one another. These students commented that the speed networking session was a nice *ice breaker* that enabled them to meet one another and more senior members of the HAB community.

There were 37 applications for travel awards from 19 countries to attend ICHA2016. The International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA), through its travel award funds, was able to support 27 students from 13 different countries. There were 71 candidates for the Maureen Keller student award, given to outstanding graduate student oral and poster communications at the ICHA conferences.

Takayama's mini-carvings, generously donated to ISSHA, reached very high prices in the auction bidding. Only Senior scientists could afford them. (Photos M. Iwatataki)

Two *Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Awards* were given this year, to Mike Quilliam and Allan Cembella. The *Patrick Gentien Young Scientist Award* was given to Dedmer Van de Waal.

The 2016 auction was a success as more than 3000 € were raised. A new feature of the auction considered a success was a student lunch with Gustaaf Hallegraef, enabling a student to obtain valuable career advice from a senior scientist (see p. 27). Stay tuned for such innovative opportunities at future auctions!

Other highlights of the 17th ICHA (2016) included a *Sea Dance*, which was available during coffee breaks. This was a motion-sensing dance designed to serve as an outreach project to explain the marine food web and blooms of algae. It is an interactive game in which the dancers get to know species and organisms that comprise our marine ecosystem while dancing to the music. It was great fun to watch our colleagues whirl around the dance floor!

Lovely textiles were available at the conference, designed by *Crubag* and sponsored by ISSHA, to represent harmful algae in artist ways. Scarves, bow ties and bags were sold; a portion of the proceeds will benefit ISSHA. The new book, *Toxic and Harmful Microalgae of the World*, by Nicolas Chomérat, Philipp Hess, Elisabeth Nézan and Patrick Lassus, was revealed at the conference and is now available at cost on the ISSHA website (see <http://www.isssha.org/News/Book-release>).

The ISSHA members were busy during the meeting and elected the following new council members to serve as your representatives: Wayne Litaker (USA), Ichiro Imai (Japan) and Po Teen Lim (Malaysia). The other Executive and Council members were re-elected for another 2 years (see new Council composition below). We thank both Mexico and Japan for submitting excellent bids for the 19th International Conference on Harmful Algae. The vote was close, and the 2020 conference will be held in Baja California, Mexico, hosted by IPN-CICIMAR in La Paz. In two years from now (2018), the 18th International Conference on Harmful Algae will be in Nantes, France, hosted by IFREMER. Stay tuned for more details about the next conferences and other news worthy items, such as job postings, work-

shops and courses, and HAB publications at the ISSHA website.

The deadline for submission of the conference proceedings is 1 March 2017, so please don't delay writing your papers. Manuscripts are a maximum of 4 pages long, with a fixed format. For more information, please go to the ISSHA website at www.isssha.org for conference photos, conference highlights and information on the format for the conference proceedings.

Vera Trainer, ISSHA President

Beatriz Reguera, ISSHA Past President

Luis Proença, Chair Local Organizing Committee for the 17th ICHA

ISSHA Officers and Council members 2016

Officers

President: Vera Trainer (USA)

1st Vice-President: Gustaaf Hallegraef (Australia)

2nd Vice-President: Wayne Litaker (USA)

Secretary: Anke Kremp (Finland)

Treasurer: Henrik Enevoldsen (Denmark)

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Godhe, Anna (Sweden)

Hess, Philipp (France)

Ichiro Imai (Japan)

Jenkinson, Ian (China, France)

Lebret, Catherine (Sweden)

Lim, Po Teen (Malaysia)

MacKenzie, Lincoln (New Zealand)

Proença, Luis (Brazil)

Tubaro, Aurelia (Italy)

The profiles of the ISSHA officers and council members can be found at <http://www.isssha.org/Society/ISSHA-Council-Members>

2016 Achievement Awards

The *Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award 2016* was given to Profs. **Mike Quilliam** and **Allan Cembella**. Short biographies of these two eminent scientists and community activists can be found at the *HAB Trail Blazers* section on the ISSHA website (www.isssha.org).

Michael A. Quilliam was recognized for outstanding contributions to the field of algal toxin chemistry and analysis. A leading analytical chemist in the field, following in the footsteps of Prof Yasumoto himself. His life-time work covers amnesic, diarrhetic, paralytic, azaspiracid, cyclic imine and cyanobacterial toxins, including the identification of many new toxin structural analogues from both marine and freshwater environments. The 'toolbox' of novel analytical methods and Certified Reference Materials (CRMs) developed by his group are now used routinely in research and regulatory laboratories worldwide and have resulted in a paradigm shift in the way algal toxins are monitored.

Mike graduated in 1977 with a PhD in Chemistry from the University of Manitoba based on research into new organosilicon reagents for synthesis, chromatography and mass spectrometry of nucleic acids. During post-doctoral research at Univ. Montréal and a subsequent appointment with the Ontario Ministry of the Environment he developed further experience in mass spectrometry and delved into the analytical chemistry of environmental contaminants. From 1978 to 1987, he

Mike Quilliam, Yasumoto Award 2016
(Photo M. Iwataki)

served as assistant and later Associate Professor of Chemistry at McMaster University focusing on detection and identification of carcinogens and their metabolites. During this time, he did some of the first work in Canada on the now standard interfacing of liquid chromatography with mass spectrometry (LC-MS). In 1987, he joined the National Research Council of Canada (NRCC), where he is now a Principal Research Officer for Biotoxin Measurement Science. He also holds an Adjunct Professorship in Chemistry at Dalhousie University. His research at NRCC has focused on the analytical chemistry of toxic substances and the production of CRMs. He has worked on various environmental and food contaminants, including polycyclic aromatic compounds and veterinary drug residues, but his main focus has been on marine and freshwater biotoxins.

Mike has published more than 240 refereed papers and book chapters and over 90 CRM certification reports. He was from 1994 to 2002 General Referee for Phycotoxins in AOAC International and from 1997 to 2001 Chairman of the "APEC Task Team on Analytical Methods and Standards for Marine Algal Toxins". He served on numerous national and international committees on shellfish toxins, such as Joint FAO/IOC/WHO Expert Group on Biotoxins in Molluscan Bivalves reporting to the *CODEX Alimentarius Commission's Committee on Fish and Fishery Products* in 2004/5. He co-organized many symposia and conferences such as toxin sessions at AOAC and the *HABTech2003 Workshop on Technologies for Monitoring of Harmful Algal Blooms and Marine Biotoxins* in New Zealand. Mike has collaborated with over 150 young and established scientists, many of whom spent time training in his laboratory. Many of these scientists now play key roles in their countries in diverse fields of toxin research and monitoring. In 2013 and 2015, Mike was included in the "Analytical Scientist's 'Power List' of 100 most influential people in the field of analytical chemistry internationally.

Allan Cembella was recognized for a long and productive scientific career entirely devoted to HABs, starting with his graduate work with Max Taylor in the 1980s. In his early studies of *Alex-*

andrium, he was one of the first to use toxin composition as a characteristic to distinguish among different strains or isolates, and was also the first to use enzyme electrophoresis to provide yet another perspective on intra-species heterogeneity. It may seem obvious that there is extensive heterogeneity with a species in these times of powerful molecular tools, but in those days, the methods for that type of investigation were far more limited and experimental, and Allan was at the forefront of that phase of discovery.

Allan continued his studies of *Alexandrium* after he moved to eastern Canada. At that time, he co-authored a paper with Christophe Destombe on the sexuality and mating dynamics of *Alexandrium* that remains a classic resource to this day. He and Destombe also published the first sequences for *Alexandrium*, opening the door to decades of work on phylogeny and molecular detection methods in that genus and many others. That was also the time he discovered the spirolide toxins and linked them to the source organism, *Alexandrium ostenfeldii* – a very nice piece of biological and chemical detective work. He remains the world's authority on spirolides. Some years later, Allan repeated this accomplishment by assembling a team at the Alfred Wegener Institute that solved the mystery of the source of azaspiracids, which until then had incorrectly been linked to a *Proto-*

Allan Cembella, Yasumoto Award 2016
(Photo M. Iwataki)

peridinium species. Many of us consider that body of work to be a scientific tour de force, as in a very short period of time, the causative organism was identified, its taxonomic and phylogenetic affinities revealed, its toxin diversity elucidated, and its global biogeography defined. Allan Cembella thus has the unique distinction of being the only person in the HAB field who has been the first to identify and fully characterize the source organisms for two major toxin families.

Allan has also been heavily involved in studies of allelopathy and in genetic studies of a variety of toxic HAB species, in collaboration with colleagues in many parts of the world. His scientific productivity is exemplary, with nearly 200 peer-reviewed papers on a wide array of topics in the HAB field.

In addition to his many scientific accomplishments, Allan has been heavily involved in HAB community activities, including serving on the *Scientific Steering Committee of GEOHAB* and chairing one of the Core Research Projects – on HABs in Fjords and Embayments. He served as Vice President of ISSHA, and has been a longstanding member of the *ICES/IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics (WGHABD)*, and has also been the German representative at many meetings of the *Intergovernmental Panel for HABs (IPHAB)*. He has been an enthusiastic and effective mentor to many students and young scientists worldwide. In addition to his educational activities in Germany, he is heavily involved and committed to HAB projects and education in Latin America, with students and projects in Chile, Argentina and Mexico.

In summary, Allan Cembella is a creative thinker with has positively impacted all of our lives and careers with broad and significant impacts in HAB research, as well as major contributions to the policy and educational aspects of our field.

The **Patrick Gentien Young Scientist Award** was given to Dedmer Van de Waal (age 34) who received his PhD in June 2010, and currently has a tenure-track position at the Netherlands Institute of Ecology. Dedmer has substantially contributed to the conceptualization of harmful algae research. His most outstanding work couples the pro-

Dedmer Van de Waal, Patrick Gentien Award 2016 (Photo M. Iwataki)

duction of stoichiometrically distinct toxins to the elemental composition of its producer, and thus linking toxin production to the general ecological framework of Ecological Stoichiometry. Doing so, he has worked across salinity boundaries and his experimental work includes various marine dinoflagellate as well as freshwater cyanobacteria species.

Dedmer not only has a cumulative record related to this work, but also two 'breakthrough' papers in *Ecology Letters*, the second highest ecological journal for which he recently also became member of the Editorial Board. Beyond this topic, his publication record (currently 29 publications), impressive for his age, is rapidly expanding.

Dedmer contributed substantially to the studies on the effects of climate change on harmful algae, notably the impacts of elevated pCO₂. His work crosses a range of organizational scales, from the regulation of genes, to eco-physiological responses (carbon and nutrient acquisition), and resource competition. Besides, his recent work includes the role of genetic diversity and phenotypic traits in the success of toxic algal blooms. Finally, Dedmer is an exceptionally creative thinker, ambitious, and active in the field of harmful algal research. He does not only bring harmful algal research to a broader scientific audience, but is also actively communicating HAB topics and respec-

tive research to the public, with various recent appearances on the Dutch national radio. Moreover, he is determined to connect HAB scientists and water managers of the Netherlands by organizing annual meetings.

Maureen Keller Student Presentation Awards

Best student oral presentation was awarded to **Alexis Fischer**, from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology – Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution Joint Program, for her contribution on “*Quantifying the chilling requirement for germinability of natural Alexandrium fundyense resting cysts*”, co-authored with Michael Brosnahan and her advisor, Donald Anderson. A California-native, Alexis moved to New England to attend Wellesley College, where she graduated with a B.A. in Biology in 2010. After a year working on *Vibrio cholerae* ecology and evolution as a research technician at the University of Alberta, she returned to New England to begin her PhD on another toxic marine microbe: *Alexandrium fundyense*. She quickly became immersed in the Anderson laboratory's intensive field program in the Nauset Marsh system (Cape Cod, MA), where *A. fundyense* form recurrent blooms. Fascinated by the seasonality of the life cycle of *A. fundyense*, Alexis began to investigate how environmental and internal factors regulated excystment. Almost 30 years since her advisor discovered the en-

dogenous annual clock in Gulf of Maine cysts, her research now addresses many of the lingering mysteries of cyst dormancy. The work presented quantifies how *A. fundyense* cysts use the environmental cue of winter chilling to restrict their germination until spring when favorable growth conditions are more likely to be sustained. This chilling response is a mechanism through which *A. fundyense*, and perhaps many other dinoflagellates, match the timing of germination to their environment, thereby maximizing bloom potential in a variety of temperature regimes and habitats. Currently, she is writing up her dissertation research, which includes experimental, observational, and modeling approaches, and considers how *A. fundyense* bloom phenology in Nauset may be affected by a changing climate.

Honorable mention for oral presentation to **Marc Long** from Université de Bretagne Occidentale (UBO, France) and University of Wollongong (UOW, Australia) for his contribution to “*Allelochemicals released by the toxic dinoflagellate Alexandrium minutum impact on Chaetoceros neogracile photosystem and viability*”. Marc undertook his studies in Brest, France, where he obtained a Bachelor in Biology of Organisms and Populations in 2013 and a Master in Marine Biology in 2015. In parallel with his university course, Marc has been working on phytoplankton physiology as a part-time research as-

Alexis Fischer, Maureen Keller Award for Best student oral presentation

Marc Long, Honorable mention for oral presentation

sistant for nearly 6 years in the laboratory of marine environmental studies (LEMAR, France) under the supervision of Dr Helene Hegaret and Dr Philippe Soudant. During his course, he also undertook overseas internships at the University of Wollongong (Australia) under the supervision of Prof D. Jolley and at the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA, Northeast Fisheries Science Center, United States) in Milford Connecticut, always working with phytoplankton physiology, with Dr Gary H. Wikfors. The work presented at ICHA2016 was obtained from his first year of PhD and highlighted the impact of the unknown allelochemicals exuded by *A. minutum* on the diatom *Chaetoceros neogracile* physiology (primarily investigating at photosystem II and cell membranes) to better understand allelochemicals mode of action. During his PhD Marc aims to characterize the allelopathic activity from the dinoflagellate *Alexandrium*. To do so, he has developed a standardized bioassay with algal cells. For the next two year of his PhD project, his main objective will be to further investigate allelochemicals mode of action and to chemically characterize the nature of allelochemicals that may also have other cytotoxic activities.

Best student poster presentation to Suema Branco for her contribution: "*Morphology and molecular description of two species of Alexandrium from a tropical estuary in southeastern Brazil: Alexandrium fragae sp. nov. and Alexandrium tamutum*". Suema was born and raised in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. She joined the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro in 2006 to do her bachelor of biology. Dr. Maringela Menezes supervised her academic studies since internship to master and Ph.D. projects. In 2012, Branco obtained her master's degree in Botany from UFRJ, whose subject of study was the taxonomy, ecology, and toxicity of marine species of Raphidophytes isolated from the Brazilian coast. In 2016 she concluded her doctorate at the UFRJ. Her thesis project was on taxonomy and phylogeny of various strains of planktonic marine dinoflagellates isolated from a tropical Brazilian estuary, mainly focusing on the potentially harmful species. In her thesis, she described a new species of

Suema Branco, Best student poster presentation

Alexandrium, *Alexandrium fragae*. She is currently a collaborating researcher in the Phycology Laboratory at the National Museum of Rio de Janeiro / UFRJ. Her primary interest is the taxonomy of harmful microalgae and the application of molecular tools in these studies.

Honorable mention for poster presentation to Jacqueline Jerney, University of Helsinki working at the Finnish Environment Institute – Marine Research Center for her poster on: "*Genetic diversity of seed banks and seasonal genotype dynamics of Alexandrium ostenfeldii (Dinophyceae) in shallow waters of the Baltic Sea*", co-authored by Conny Sjqvist, Sanna Suikkanen, Satoshi Nagai and Anke Kremp. Jacqueline was born in Austria, where she grew up and started her academic career. She studied ecology at the University of Vienna,

Jacqueline Jerney, Honorable mention for poster presentation

focused on Limnology during her studies and found her passion for phycology on the way. Jacqueline wrote her Master's thesis about algae turf scrubbers used for restoration of eutrophic waters and graduated in 2012. Afterwards she gained experience in the applied field of algal research at the University of Vienna, the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, and the company Erber Future Business in Austria. Doing so, she started missing ecology and basic research, which prompted her to start her PhD in Finland. Currently she is working on her PhD studies, supervised by Anke Kremp and Sanna Suikkanen at the Finnish Environment Institute. The main topic is ecological and evolutionary significance of seed banks for the expansion of phytoplankton blooms in the Baltic Sea.

Luis Proena (Chair) and members of his Local Organizing Committee receive a *Gymnodinium catenatum* carving as an ISSHA recognition for their strong commitment to make the 17 ICHA a success.

New Auction Item: Lunch with a famous HAB scientist

Lunch with a famous HAB scientist: PhD student Sara Harðardóttir and Prof Gustaaf Hallegraeff.

A new experiment during the ISSHA auction was the opportunity for students to bid for a **lunch opportunity with a famous HAB scientist**. During a delightful lunch at the Florianopolis

food market Prof Gustaaf Hallegraeff thus offered his career counseling services to Copenhagen PhD student Sara Harðardóttir (pictured). At his home university in Tasmania Gustaaf offers

annual workshops on what it takes to become a successful researcher (passion, creativity, traveling, thinking global, communication skills, building teams, daring to take risks etc). Needless to say Sara already ticked many of those boxes, and Gustaaf was pleased to note that promising postdoc career options and contacts he suggested had already been approached by the end of the conference week. For a student it can be a challenge to network at the busy ICHA conference and for Sara the opportunity to meet and receive counselling from Gustaaf was much welcomed and rewarding. Altogether, a successful experience for both, and worth repeating.

10th International Conference on Toxic Cyanobacteria

The 10th International Conference on Toxic Cyanobacteria was held in Wuhan, China from 23 to 28th October 2016. The conference is held every three years and brings together around 300 researchers from around the world to present their research findings. Toxic cyanobacterial blooms continue to be a major concern in freshwater systems worldwide and the recent blooms in Lake Erie, USA were highlighted, as well as the ongoing blooms in Lake Taihu and others in China. The dominant toxic species continues to be *Microcystis aeruginosa* but there were also a number of talks about *Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii*, *Dolicospermum* (previously *Anabaena*) *circinalis* and the benthic genus *Phormidium*. There was a strong emphasis on mitigation strategies, including the use of hydrogen peroxide and clay products, as well as new and faster detection methods. Molecular methods to understand bloom dynamics was a strong focus of the conference, and the integration of these methods with tra-

ditional ecological and physiological approaches.

One evening was devoted to a discussion of cyanobacterial management strategies and during this session, Michele Burford, a committee member on the newly formed IOC and SCOR funded GlobalHAB consortium, gave a talk on the aims of GlobalHAB and invited conference participants to be en-

gaged. There was considerable interest, particularly from Chinese participants, and further information on the GlobalHAB on the new website is eagerly awaited.

Michele Burford, Australia Rivers Institute, Griffith University, Nathan, QLD, Australia

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Fig. 1. At the conference dinner. Left to right: Cheryl Orr, Tim Davis, Phil Orr, Michele Burford and Anusuya Willis

From left to right and from top to bottom: 1-5, happy faces at the 17 ICHA; 6-8, frantic activity and fun at the ISSHA auction; 9, ISSHA table; 10, dancer from the local "Escola de Samba" teaching the Brazilian rhythms to the participants after the conference banquet (all photos by Mathias Schramm except n° 6, from Mitsunori Iwataki)

New book

NEW! Toxic and Harmful Microalgae of the World Ocean

This ISSHA and IOC UNESCO publication, written by Patrick Lassus, Nicolas Chomérat, Philipp Hess, and Elisabeth Nézan constitutes the first ever global compendium on harmful algal blooms (HAB), microorganisms that deplete fish stocks, destroy fish farms and bring disease and death both to humans and to large sea animals.

In a case-by-case review of data on major harmful algal bloom incidents,

the publication sounds the alert on increasing trends, as observed, for example, along the coasts of Florida (USA), where data has been compiled since the mid-19th century, India and Oman. In the Adriatic and Baltic seas, harmful algal incidents are on the increase despite governmental awareness and decisions to restrict the production and discharge of phosphate and other harmful chemicals.

This book updates available information from international databases on toxic and harmful species of phytoplankton and micro-phytobenthos. It lists regional occurrences at world-wide scale: localities, cell densities, toxicity

levels in contaminated animals, human and animal poisoning, isolation of identified active molecules and toxins, documentary sources. Finally, this book addresses the geographic distributions of phycotoxin-producers from recent data. The objective is to analyze the evolution of toxic and harmful episodes over the past 30 years to identify trends, and to introduce a discussion on the reality of a time-dependent increase in the number of known species and toxins.

Order at the ISSHA website www.issha.org web shop.

Price (postage included) is 50 €

Philipp Hess, one of the book authors and Vera Trainer, President of ISSHA, present the new book at the 17 ICHA in Florianópolis, Brazil

Robert RL Guillard (1921-2016) In Memoriam¹

Robert 'Bob' Guillard was an icon in all senses of the word, and many tributes have and will be written [1, 2] This is but a brief overview of a life very well-lived and shared.

Born in New York City on February 5th, 1921, Bob's love for the natural environment was firmly established during his time with his grandparents in Stonington, Connecticut. An early scholar, Bob completed grammar school in 7 years, graduated from Townsend Harris High School in New York City in 3 years, and earned a B.S. in Physics (City College New York, CCNY) at the age of 20. Bob was hired by the U.S. Navy to install and maintain antimagnetic mine equipment. He continued to pursue course work in the evenings and taught at New York University and CCNY. During this time he was smitten by a botany professor and decided that he wanted to become a 'naturalist'. He went to Yale in 1949 and received a Master's degree (1951) on route to his Ph.D. (1954) under the tutelage of G. Evelyn Hutchinson. Soon after, he was awarded a summer fellowship to the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute - he changed fields from botany to oceanography. After a short period in Hawaii, Bob was hired by the U.S. Bureau of Commercial Fisheries Marine Laboratory in Milford, Connecticut where he was challenged by Victor Loosanoff with the task of 'figuring out how to grow oysters'. As Bob recounted it, his first thought was that the little oysters would need to be fed and he reasoned that they were partial to what was in the water column. That was when he began isolating phytoplankton and developing the techniques to culture them in volume. His first publication was in the *Proceedings of the National Shellfisheries Association* and it launched shellfish aquaculture as we know it today - the path to f/2 was being laid. That first paper demonstrated that individual phytoplankton isolates differed in their nutritional value to oysters, thereby establishing the foundation for "the Milford Method" of feeding hatchery seed of shellfish selected strains of microalgae later further developed by Ravenna Ukeles and others. Without Bob's pioneering work

in phytoplankton culture and nutritional value, the rearing of shellfish in captivity would not be possible.

In 1958, John Ryther recruited Bob to Woods Hole where he was a senior scientist and in 1981, he moved to the recently established Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences and established the collection of algae and other microscopic marine organisms that was designated by Congress as the *Provasoli-Guillard National Center for Culture of Marine Phytoplankton* - to honor two men whose research and mentoring had provided the world with a first-class source of algae for research and aquaculture. Anybody in the field of algal culture knows 'f/2' - but few realize that this was but a sideline for Bob. He was a global leader in the physiological ecology of phytoplankton. Bob reduced the curiosity that drove his science to this question: "Why do they live where they do?" Considering that phytoplankton cannot control their position, the question becomes almost metaphysical and leads one into the "n-dimensional hyperspace (Bob's phrase)" of physics, chemistry, and biology combined. Bob excelled at creating an environment in

which ephemeral microbes could thrive and be sustained, and in 1962, he published a paper with John Ryther that became one of the most cited papers in marine science (over 4700 citations at last note) as it described in detail the most successful algal-culture medium ever developed [3].

Bob was anything but a one-dimensional scientist. He had a wide array of interests and talents outside the laboratory, including fencing (he was an instructor), Morris dancing (one of the best in the country), target shooting (his keenness for guns was legendary), and Transcendental Meditation, an activity that he shared with his wife Ruth, a TM teacher. His penchant for collecting all manner of what most would deem junk was well known - and those same doubters always knew where to go when they needed some esoteric item. Bob was recycling long before it was a word!

Bob's publication record was impressive by any standard and his advice was in constant demand. Ever the teacher, one frequently got far more than they bargained for when they asked what they initially deemed a 'simple question'. Out-of-the-blue phone calls that began with the words, "I've been thinking..." could lead to lifetimes worth of questions needing answers. There are countless 'Bob stories' and, while some are suitable for publication, these will be saved for later celebrations. He was generous with his time and expertise and never lost his curiosity and questioning mind. In 1995 Bob was named an *Honored Life Member of the National Shellfisheries Association* [4], and in 1998 he was presented with the *Honorary Life Member Award from the World Aquaculture Society*.

Bob passed away in his sleep on September 25, 2016 in Boothbay Harbor, Maine, leaving behind his wife of 53 years, Ruth, 3 stepsons and their families, and a barn full of decades of accumulated treasures - "just in case I need them someday" (including, one presumes, all those boxes of little blue paper circles that separate Millipore filters).

Bob would scoff at all the attention

Bob proudly showing his cultures to a visitor (photo from the Bigelow Laboratory website)

being paid to his accomplishments. His curiosity was at the core of his existence and this, his keen intellect, and sharp wit were evident after even the shortest discussion with him. Scholar, old Yankee, friend - it was an honor, privilege, and most entertaining to have known him.

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¹Text and figure reproduced from the *World Aquaculture Magazine* 47(4), December 2016 with permission from the authors.

More information about Bob Guillard, the father of the f/2 medium, at the Bigelow Laboratory website

<https://www.bigelow.org/news/articles/2016-10-04-2.html>

Beautiful wooden carvings of harmful dinoflagellates, from Prof Takayama, made for the ISSHA 2016 awardees. From left to right: *Dinophysis fortii*, *Alexandrium tamarense*, *Gymnodinium catenatum* and *Takayama pulchella*.

Forthcoming events

Crossing disciplinary boundaries across the freshwater-marine continuum to advance the understanding of harmful algal blooms (HABs)

This session (012), to be held during the next ASLO meeting (Honolulu, Hawaii, 26 Feb – 3 March), seeks to bring together HABs scientists who study multiple aspects of these events, including their biogeochemistry, chemistry, biogeography, toxicology, ecology, and epidemiology, as well as approaches to monitor HAB distribution, genetic diversity, and toxicity. All types of HABs studies are encouraged including descriptive, correlative, empirical, and/or theoretical. Given the environmental and health threat that HABs pose to society, we encourage a focus on management solutions

NOTE:

Abstract submission deadline was October 14.

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ICMSS 2017: Protecting consumers, assuring supply, growing confidence

Now that the excitement of the Brazilian ICHA conference is over it is time to start looking towards 2017 and we are delighted to inform you that the **International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety, ICMSS 2017**, will be hosted by The Marine Institute, Galway Ireland from May 14 - 18, 2017. This is the 11th conference in this series and offers an important multidisciplinary interface between regulatory, scientific and industrial representatives of the international molluscan food safety community. It is a biannual forum where unusual, emerging and novel shellfish risk factors are discussed, offering new information and solutions. The Marine Institute in association with *Bord Iascaigh Mhara*, The Food Safety Authority of Ireland, The Sea Fisheries Protection Authority and The Irish Shellfish Association will host the conference in the wonderful state of the art conference centre of the National University in Galway.

Ireland has a distinguished track record in the area of molluscan shellfish safety, in developing state of the art monitoring protocols, forecasting tools and a variety of cutting edge research activities. This is the second time the conference has been in Galway and we

look forward to welcoming old friends and new to our conference on the theme of *"Protecting consumers, assuring supply, growing confidence"*. **ICMSS 2017** will include several keynote presentations from acclaimed international experts in the area. A series of workshops will be held in conjunction with the event on the 19th and 20th May. We encourage attendance from shellfish safety professionals and students including, microbiologists, toxin chemists, toxicologists, marine scientists, regulators, policy makers, food safety specialists, environmental health officials, engineers, environmental managers, academics and undergraduate and postgraduate students.

We invite you to join us for a stimulating conference to be held in a collaborative atmosphere in the vibrant and welcoming city of Galway on Europe's western margin. We promise a very exciting international event, providing an opportunity to bring together experts from all over the world to exchange ideas, information and the most up to date findings, allowing us to review current state of the art and future prospects in molluscan shellfish safety. So, don't hesitate to come and get involved. The abstract call is open at www.icmss2017.com and register for what promises to be a fantastic conference!

For more information see icmss2017.

com, follow twitter (#ICMSS17) or contact the conference convener Joe Silke (joe.silke@marine.ie)

Important Dates:

- Call for Abstracts Opens - 09/2016
- Abstract Submission Close - 12/2016
- Early Bird Registration Close - 02/2017
- Conference Opening - 05/2017

18th ICHA in Nantes, France, to be held 21-26 October 2018 – save the date!

The 18th International Conference on Harmful Algae will be held in Nantes, France. The conference venue has been booked for the dates from 21 to 26 October 2018 by IFREMER, the institutional host of the conference. Philipp Hess (IFREMER) and the French delegation (Research Network PHYCOTOX) gave a presentation of the project, the city and progress made in the organisation. A professional conference organiser will assist the local and scientific organising committees, and is about to be appointed. The website will operate from early 2017 and separate announcements will be posted through the conference mailing list and the ISSHA website – watch this space!

Philipp Hess (IFREMER, France) takes up the torch during the torch-taking ceremony of the 18th ICHA in 2018.

11th International Conference on Modern and Fossil Dinoflagellates (DINO 11)

2nd Circular and Call for Workshop Proposals
 11th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MODERN AND FOSSIL DINOFLAGELLATES
 17 to 21 July 2017, Bordeaux (France)

DINO11, the 11th International Conference on *Modern and Fossil Dinoflagellates* will be held at Bordeaux University, France, during July 17-21, 2017.

The scientific program will be devoted to the latest developments in studies of living and fossil dinoflagellates, this group being one of the most important among planktonic and benthic marine

microalgae, and as such gathering both biological and geological interests.

All information about the conference can be found at the conference website <http://laplf.org/dino11/news.htm>

Ninth Symposium on Harmful Algae in the US (Maryland, 11-17 November 2017)

The National HAB Committee (NHC) is proud to announce the Ninth Symposium on Harmful Algae will be held in Baltimore, Maryland from November 11-17, 2017.

The theme of the Ninth Symposium will be *Training the Next Generation* and include several hands on workshops for the students and postdoctoral fellows. <http://www.who.edu/habsymposia/>

Soon coming: Guide for designing and implementing a plan to monitor toxin-producing microalgae

This Manual is a joint product of the IAEA and the IOC of UNESCO. The first edition was published in Spanish in 2011 and is available on line at the IOC-HAB website.

With the initiation of additional IAEA national and regional projects on HABs, the organization of regular IOC global and regional training courses, and the strengthened cooperation between the IOC and the IAEA on board capacity development, the need developed to translate this HAB manual into English, and expand it with the addi-

tion of chapters related to benthic HAB species. That was a natural next step to assist Member States to implement monitoring programmes to detect potentially toxic HABs species in their respective coastal waters.

This manual is intended as an introduction to basic analytical techniques that can be applied when designing a standard sampling protocol for both planktonic and benthic microalgae (and associated environmental conditions) and vectors of biotoxins (shellfish and fish). This standardization of methods

will enable more robust data comparisons between countries and will yield improved risk assessments of potentially toxic HABs events.

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Please feel free to contact any of the editors if you have article, ideas for article or special issues and we will work with you!

Deadline

Deadline to submit material for HAN 56:
28 February 2017

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